

Influence of Access to Financial Resources on Sustainable Performance of Small and Medium Enterprises in Uasin Gishu County, Kenya

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Abstract

The small- and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) play critical role in creating job opportunities and growth of the economy. Currently, the rate at which the new firms formed have stagnated and those that have been in business for less than five years are closing down at a high and this is clearly illustrated on this study that investigates the effect of access to financial resources on sustainable performance of SMEs in Uasin Gishu County. The study adopted Pecking Order Theory. Descriptive research design was applied to conduct the study which targeted a population of 450 registered enterprises in Uasin Gishu County. Simple random sampling technique was used to select 135 samples SMEs and primary data was collected using questionnaires. Collected data was coded, cleaned and then analyzed to measure completeness of the information obtained using Statistical Program for Social Sciences (SPSS V26). Inferential data analysis was carried out to determine the relationship between variables using linear regression analysis. From linear regression model ($R^2 = .747$) indicating that access to financial resources account for 74.7% of sustainable performance of SMEs and there was a positive significant relationship between access to financial resource ($\beta_1=0.935$ and $p<0.05$) and sustainable performance of SMEs. Access to financial resource had significant influence on sustainability of small and medium enterprises performance. The access to financial resource positively influences sustainable performance of SMEs in Uasin Gishu County. The study concluded that access to financial resources positively influence the sustainable performance of SMEs. The study recommended financial institutions to create favorable policies to enable SMEs access loans easily. The study recommended government to offer incentives and funding to SMEs at a lower cost to sustain their financial performance.

Keywords: Access, resource, sustainable, Financial, Performance

Introduction

The importance of finances has been viewed as a critical element for financial performance of small and medium-sized enterprises. Limit to financial hinder growth and development of these firms (Levy, 2015). As small- and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) are typically resource-constrained, the issue of SMEs' sustainable growth often attracts significant attention from not only academics but also policymakers (McKelvie & Wiklund 2010 and Wright, Roper, Hart, and Carter, 2015). Poor management and accounting practices is also a major factor that hinders financial performance of these firms, and it hampers the ability of smaller enterprises to raise finance. Researchers have also acknowledged lack of access to external finance and weak capital base, inexperience in the field of business, particularly lack of technical knowledge plus inadequate managerial skills, lack of planning and lack of market research as causes of small business failure (Van Stel and Storey 2004).

Several studies on sustainable entrepreneurship argued that sustainable entrepreneurship can be explained with opportunity recognition and entrepreneurship (Kuckertz & Wagner, 2010).

In many developing countries, small and medium enterprises (SMEs) constitute the bulk of industrial base (Kormawa, Wohlmuth & Devlin, 2011). Today's dynamic environment requires SMEs to be entrepreneurial if they are to survive, grow or have superior performance (Fairoz, Hirofumi & Tanaka, 2010). Firm-level entrepreneurship is key to enhancement of firm performance of small firms (Patel & D'Souza, 2012).

Financing of small- and medium-sized entities (SMEs) has been a subject of debate between policymakers, researchers, and other stakeholders globally. For SMEs to finance their daily activities and perform well, a healthy financial position is critical, more importantly, a significant positive networking capital (current assets minus current liabilities) position (Bhunja 2010). To finance these critical activities, various sources of finance exist, which therefore makes their accessibility more critical to SMEs, as they determine their performance and continued existence. These include formal (long-term and short-term debt, equity from entity owner, among others) and informal sources comprising loans from friends and immediate family members (Fatoki & Asah 2011).

The debate is fueled by the important role that SMEs continue to play in the private sector across the globe and includes employment creation (Ayyagari et al. 2016; Naude & Chiweshe 2017).

From a global perspective, Stouraitis, Harun and Kyritsis (2017) cited Gerlach-Kristen, O'Connell, and O'Toole (2015) indicating that SMEs contributed towards 50% of the global GDP and 60% of global employment. In keeping with the foregoing, Bernard, Stabilito and Yoo (2010) argued that inadequate access to financial services is one of the main constraints facing entities in their bid to enter the export market. Beck and Demirguc-Kunt (2006) also echoed the same sentiments, stating that SMEs are financially more constrained than large firms and are less likely to have access to formal finance (long-term loans). From a regional perspective, Irene (2017) cited Abor and Quarterly (2010) and provided a Southern African perspective stating that SMEs contributed 57% towards the gross domestic product (GDP) and accounted for 61% of jobs created in the country.

Vanacker, Collewaert and Zahra (2016), study across 26 European countries, found evidence that slack financial resources (more than the required minimum level for operational purposes) enhanced the entity's performance level. The access to and availability of finance plays a pivotal role in the performance of SMEs. Balamoune-Lutz and Lutz (2017) surveyed 25 500 female-owned firms (only) in the Middle East and Africa. The results indicate that inadequate access to financial resource significantly contributed to poor entity performance. In other words, owing to poor access to financial resource, SMEs find it challenging to live up to their performance outcomes (Karedza et al. 2014). In Zimbabwe Zindiye (2008) pointed out that because of inadequate access to financial resource, SMEs are without the capacity to buy quality raw materials to produce quality goods and services that adhere to international standards, expected of firms competing in the global market.

In fact, studies show that about 20% of SMEs in Africa have a clear line to credit from banks. Research on SMEs growth has revealed that the rate at which small firms fail in developing economies in Africa is greater than in the already developed economies (Ihua, 2009). Fafchamps and Schündeln (2013) examined the relationship between local financial development and firm performance in Morocco. Fanta et al. (2017), in their study on four SADC countries, namely Malawi, Mozambique, Zambia and Zimbabwe, highlighted that about 50% of small business owners in Zimbabwe start and grow their entrepreneurial endeavors out of their own money and a third out of informal finance. Financial institutions in many countries in Africa do not avail SMEs with adequate finance.

In Tanzania, Boermans and Willebrands (2011) analysed the influence of financial constraints on firm performance and Berman and Hericourt (2009) found that availability of finance played a big role in the entity's decision to engage in buying and selling of goods or services at a global stage. Atieno (2009) examined linkages between access to financial resource and the performance of small-scale enterprises in Kenya.

According to Sessional Paper No.2 of 2005, SMEs sector contribution to GDP in Kenya rose from 13.8% to about 18% between 1993 and 1999. Economic survey (2017) reported that lately contribution to the Kenya's GDP is approximately 33% by the sector. According to Were (2016), considering the global production capacity especially in the developed countries, it is a challenge for countries from Africa, Kenya included SMEs for poverty eradication. In Kenya, SMEs in the informal sector outperform services SMEs in terms of growth and expansion, with 31% expansion of the former relative to 24 % expansion of the latter (Were, 2016). SMEs need to realize financial performance if they must expand.

According to Al-shami (2008) measures of financial performance are profitability and turnover. Access to financial resource is a major challenge hindering financial growth of start-up SMEs (Mazanai & Fatoki, 2012). According to Haron, Ibrahim, Nor and Ibrahim, (2013) credit processing by financial institutions is becoming too complex for SMEs in most growing economies and this becomes a problem in accessing the finance they require to scale up. An observation by Pretorius and Shaw (2004) was that a big number of SMEs depend on owners' contributions and family, or friends support, and this may not be adequate for SMEs financial growth. External finance accessibility is thus crucial in availing adequate funds for SMEs.

Objectives of the study

The main purpose to conduct this research is to determine the influence of access to financial resources on sustainable performance of Small and Medium Enterprises in Uasin Gishu county. The survey also wanted to establish policies that the government can put in place that would be favorable to provide financial access which would boast sustainable performance.

Statement of the Problem

Despite the importance of SMEs to the Kenyan economy, the rate at which new firms are formed have stagnated and the already existing SMEs are being limited the potential to grow (Ngui, 2014).

For Kenya to realize the vision 2030 of being an industrialized economy, an effort should be put to promote the SME industry and this can be made possible by investigating what really can improve the financial performance of the enterprises. Access to resource is the engine behind the sustainable performance because without enough funds for working capital and investments no firm can survive. However, SMEs are faced with constraints as they endeavor to access finance from financial institutions (Nyambura, 2013). Most studies are on the general performance of SMEs neglecting the fact that SMEs must be financially fit to attain financial growth and solve economic problems. Not much has been done on the effect of access to financial resources on sustainable performance of SMEs in areas that have high levels of poverty as most studies in the developed economies. Further, most of these studies have not narrowed down to specific sectors of the economy, for instance trade, processing, manufacturing, or service sectors. For this reason, therefore, it was important for the government to provide to access to financial resources to be able to boast sustainable performance of SMEs in Uasin Gishu County.

Theoretical Framework

This study adopted a Pecking Order Theory (POT) pioneered in year 1961 by Donaldson. The theory states that, in making a choice on sources of finance, managers should follow a particular hierarchy that provides the first preference to internal sources followed by external financing. The external sources give priority to debt financing then finally considers equity financing as the last option. Pronca, Laureanoa and Laureanoa (2014) asserted that small enterprises prefer internal financing to external financing. If internal funds are inadequate, then according to Proenca et al (2014) the firms prefer short- term debts to long-term debts. Informed managers go for internal financing while optimistic managers choose to maximize profit of a firm by supplementing internal financing with debt financing. (Chen, Chen, Chen & Huang, 2013)

In accordance with the finance theory, only the permanent portion of working capital should be financed through long-term debt (Gitman 2000). This leaves the financing of non-permanent working capital to short-term sources of finance, namely trade credit, bank overdraft, tax provisions and short-term bank loans among other alternative current liabilities that can be used to fund non-permanent working capital requirements (Padachi, Howorth & Narasimhan 2012). In situations where a negative net working capital exists, short-term sources of funding could as well be used to finance non-current assets; by so doing, the aggressive approach will have been adopted

(Bhattacharya 2001). Research provides evidence that SMEs mostly prefer the use of informal sources of finance (Padachi et al. 2012). This is a strategy that majority of SMEs implement solely to maintain firm ownership.

Despite finance costs associated with debt financing, Proenca et al (2014) pointed out managers who are risk averse will still prefer external financing. A research study by Zoppa and McMahon (2002) revealed that about 75% of SMEs makes financial decisions with conformity to pecking order theory. According to Cassar and Holmes (2003), the Pecking order theory conforms to SMEs since most of them are owner managed and thus, they would not wish to dilute their businesses control. This theory is of great importance to this study because it provides an insight on sources of finance and the best modalities that can be put in place by SMEs in accessing finance.

Literature Review

Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) have a significant role in employment and contribute to the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) (Sarwoko & Frisdiantara, 2016). The role of SMEs is significant for economic development and employment development. SMEs can achieve a competitive advantage and contribute significantly to regional and national economic growth and public welfare. SMEs also have significant environmental impacts at regional and national levels. Constraints faced in the development of SMEs today include access to markets and capital, information technology, and the lack of competent human resources (HR). Increasing employee competency through training with traditional methods such as lectures, seminars, and short courses does not always support SME operational training, but skills through training and education based on results, the use of interactive workshops based on action learning and role-playing, are recommended for SMEs' sustainability (Urban & Naidoo, 2012).

There is a study on the relationship between sustainability orientation and performance of new product development showing a positive relationship between them (Claudy, Peterson & Pagell, 2016). This study indicates that a high sustainability orientation enables the company to enhance operational efficiencies and cost savings. Consequently, sustainability entrepreneurship could be a possible solution to sustainability issues through business activities and could form a sustainable entrepreneurial ecosystem. In a study of Soto-Acosta, Cismaru (2016) which analyzed the relationship between sustainable entrepreneurship and business performance, they found that sustainable entrepreneurship of small and medium-sized enterprises was associated with people

(including community, partners, and workforce), and planet (including environment, resources, and technologies).

Firm performance is directly dependent on access to long-term and short-term finance. Vanacker, Collewaert and Zahra (2016), relying on longitudinal data from 162 633 European entities across 26 countries, found evidence that slack financial resources (more than the required minimum level for operational purposes) enhanced the entity's performance level. However, the higher the slack level of financial resources, the lower the entity's performance enhancement was. They further provided evidence that in European countries where weak credit rights were found, abundant financial resources had a positive effect on entity performance. The access to and availability of finance plays a pivotal role in the performance of SMEs.

Baliamoune-Lutz and Lutz (2017) recently surveyed 25 500 female-owned firms (only) in the Middle East and Africa. The results indicate that inadequate access to financial resource significantly contributed to poor entity performance. Zindiye (2008) concurred and pointed out that because of inadequate access to financial resource, SMEs are without the capacity to buy quality raw materials to produce quality goods and services that adhere to international standards, expected of firms competing in the global market. In other words, owing to poor access to financial resource, SMEs find it challenging to live up to their performance outcomes (Karedza et al. 2014). Access to financial resource is the key determinant of SME performance in Zimbabwe (World Bank Ghana Office 2013). Fanta et al. (2017), in their study on four SADC countries, namely Malawi, Mozambique, Zambia and Zimbabwe, highlighted that about 50% of small business owners in Zimbabwe start and grow their entrepreneurial businesses out of their own money and a third out of informal finance. He mentioned that in Zimbabwe, a maximum of only 2.3% of SMEs have access to bank credit, 11.3% from informal finances, 1.6% from other formal sources and none from trade. This is so because informal loans are small; they are mostly used in small business performance for financing operations (working capital) rather than growth (expansion) (Fanta 2012) and informal lenders charge unreasonably high interest rates that erode profit of small firms.

Gombarume (2014) in a study on 100 SMEs in Chitungwiza, Zimbabwe, noted that most of the SMEs were not getting enough financial support from financial institutions and were thus not performing well. Tinarwo (2016) highlighted that because of the buyer denominated market, where buyers negotiate and bargain until prices are lowered unprofitably, the operators of SMEs in

Zimbabwe have resorted to producing substandard products. This enables them to conserve costs, leading to poor SME performance because customers begin to lose confidence in doing business with SMEs operating on the market and this forces them to source alternatives.

Macharia (2012) pursued a study with an objective of determining the extent to which accessibility to finance affect small and micro enterprise investments in Ongata Rongai Town. The findings of the study where that an average of 40% of these finances came from family and friends, 30% came from business savings and 24% came from financial institutions. Further, the study revealed the obstacles faced by SMEs in accessing funds were their collateral requirements, guarantors' requirements, banks procedures in vetting and cost of loans. Recommendation for the study was that banks should provide better environment for small firms to access loans.

Nyambura (2013) in a study to find out determinants of investments in the informal venture capital market in Kenya revealed that in developing economies, where financial institutions have remarkable progress, SMEs are still faced with obstacles as they try to access finance from these institutions. According to the study, even though SMEs constitute the largest number of customers for commercial banks, finances extended to them are mainly short term and hence denying them long term investments. Recommendations were that the government should think of a fund for SMEs to access loans at low cost.

Mugo (2012) conducted a study to assess determinants of women entrepreneurs' financial performance in Nairobi Central Business District (CBD). The objectives of the study were to gauge their access to financial resource, to examine effect of budgeting on their performance, assess challenges in record keeping and to examine working capital management influence on performance. The study identified finance being the main impediment influencing women entrepreneurs' performance. It recommended that a product special to women entrepreneurs should be developed by banks to improve their access to loans.

A study by Kinyua (2014) to establish factors that determine SMEs performance in Nakuru town Jua Kali Sector with an objective to examine what role is played by finance, found out that finance accessibility positively affected performance of SMEs. The study recommended that the financial institutions should improve availability of funds in this sector by improving their lending conditions and requirements.

Conceptual framework.

To bring into view how access of financial resources by the SMEs would boast sustainable performance, linear regression analysis is done by two variables; Sustainable performance of SMEs which is the dependent variable and the predictor variable being access to financial resources.

Research Methodology

The study used a descriptive research design. Descriptive survey design provided tools for describing collections of statistical observations and reducing information to an understandable form. Out of all the SMEs in Uasin Gishu county, the survey targeted a population comprised of 450 small and medium enterprises. This population was partitioned into groups using stratified random sampling depending on the services and products they offer. This study used simple random sampling technique to select the 135 entrepreneurs who participated in this study. Simple random sampling was used as a major sampling technique because each respondent had an equal chance of inclusion in the sample. Data was collected using questionnaires. The questionnaire was administered to the managers, employees and some customers of SMEs from each of the selected firms. After data collection, the researcher conducted data cleaning to improve the quality of the responses. The research yielded quantitative data. The questionnaire was coded and analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS V 26). Descriptive statistics included the use of frequencies, and percentages, while the inferential statistics including linear regression.

Results

The survey had a response rate of 98.5%, and this accounted for the 133 questionnaires that were dully filled and the remaining 1.5% accounts for the 2 questionnaires that were not dully filled. A linear regression model was used to explore the access to financial resources on sustainable performance of small and medium enterprises. The R^2 represented the measure of variability in sustainability of SMEs that access to financial resources accounted for.

Table 1: Model Summary on access to financial resources and sustainable performance of SMEs

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.864 ^a	.747	.744	.34371

a. Predictors: (Constant), Resources

From the model, ($R^2 = .747$) shows that access to financial resource account for 74.7% variation in sustainable performance. Access to financial resources predictor used in the model captured the variation in the sustainable performance as shown in Table 2

Table 2: Analysis of Variance on financial resources and sustainable performance of SMEs

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	35.562	1	35.562	301.019	.000 ^b
	Residual	12.050	102	.118		
	Total	47.612	103			

a. Dependent Variable: Sustainable performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), Resources

The analysis of variance was used to test whether the model significantly fit in predicting the outcome than using the mean as shown in (Table 2). The regression model with financial resources as a predictor was significant ($F=301.02$, p value =0.001) shows that there is a significant access to financial resources on sustainable performance of small and medium enterprises.

$$Y = 0.248 + 0.935X + 0.205 \dots\dots\dots \text{Equation 1}$$

Where: Y = Sustainable performance of SMEs, X = access to financial resources, ϵ = error term

In addition, the β coefficients for access to financial resources as independent variable were generated from the model. The results obtained from Equation 1 indicate that for every unit change in financial resources there would be 0.935 performance.

Table 3: Financial resources and sustainable performance of SMEs

Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.248	.205		1.214	.227
	Resources	.935	.054	.864	17.350	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Sustainable performance

Table 3 shows the estimates of β -value and gave the contribution of the predictor to the model.

The β -value for access to financial resources had a positive coefficient, depicting positive relationship with sustainable performance of SMEs as summarized in the model.

From the findings the t-test associated with β -values was significant and access to financial resource as the predictor was making a significant contribution to the model. The study hypothesized that there is no significant influence of access to financial resource on sustainable performance of SMEs.

Findings

The study findings showed that there was a positive significant influence of access to financial resource ($\beta_1=0.935$ and $p < 0.05$) sustainable performance of SMEs. Therefore, an increase in access to financial resource led to higher sustainable performance of SMEs. The findings revealed a positive influence of access to financial resources on sustainable performance of the SMEs.

The major source of finance for processing SMEs was short term loans from financial institutions and followed by savings and then donations from family and friends. However, loans from banks were not readily available and accessible to start-up processing SMEs. The findings are supported by Kinyua (2014) study who established that the accessibility to finance positively affected the performance of SMEs.

Conclusion

The major source of resource for the SMEs is the loans from the financial institutions, business savings, and donations from family and friends. The study concludes financial and human capital

resources are important in the sustainable performances of SMEs. The access to financial resources influences the sustainable performance of the SMEs.

Recommendations

The study recommended the government to create favorable policies to enable SMEs to access finance through loans easily. This is likely to boost the financial performance of the SMEs since they will have enough financial resources to invest.

The study recommends the SMEs entrepreneurs should be encouraged to acquire the human and financial resources and set business goals and maximize the utilization of these resources adequately.

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